

humantech

D6.1– HT micro-learning unit descriptors

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement n° 101058236. This document reflects only the author's view, and the EU Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

D6.1 – HT Micro Learning Unit Descriptors

Project Title	Human-Centred Technologies for a Safer and Greener European Construction Industry.
Project Acronym	HumanTech
Grant Agreement No	101058236
Instrument	Research & Innovation Action
Topic	HORIZON-CL4-2021-TWIN-TRANSITION-01-12
Start Date of Project	June 1, 2022
Duration of Project	36 months

Name of the Deliverable	HT micro-learning unit descriptors
Number of the Deliverable	D6.1 (D26)
Related WP Number and Name	WP6
Related Task Number and Name	T6.1
Deliverable Dissemination Level	PU - Public
Deliverable Due Date	Month 20
Deliverable Submission Date	31 January 2024
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D6.1 – HT Micro Learning Unit Descriptors

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Keywords

Training, Micro-Learning Units, Upskilling, Reskilling

Revisions

Version	Submission date	Comments	Author
v0.1	31 January 2024	Final Version	Martin Breen and Gloria Callinan TUS

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
2D	Two-dimensional
3D	Three-dimensional
BIM	Building Information Modelling
bSDD	buildingSMART Data Dictionaries
CAD	Computer assisted design
CB	Construction Blueprint
CDE	Common Data Environments
DSDT	Dynamic Semantic Digital Twins
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
H&S	Health and Safety
HE	Higher Education
HT	HumanTech
IFC	International Foundation Class
MLU	Micro-Learning Units
OER	Open Educational Resources
SMEs	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicles
UGV	Unmanned Ground Vehicles
VET	Vocational education and training
WP	Work Package
XR	Extended Reality

Abstract

This deliverable presents the HT micro-learning unit descriptors and the steps taken to archive these results. Based on the work carried out in WP6 of the HumanTech project, the descriptors of 12 modules, their content and the corresponding ULOs have been shared in this paper. These Micro-Learning Units will go on to be developed through the remainder of the HumanTech project and training will then be carried out with HEI, VET and industry professional. This is a collaborative process and the HumanTech partners and project results will heavily influence the resulting training material.

The HumanTech project

The European construction industry faces three major challenges: increase the safety and wellbeing of its workforce, improve its productivity, and become greener, making efficient use of resources.

To address these challenges, HumanTech proposes to develop **human-centred cutting-edge technologies** such as wearables for workers' safety and support and robots that can harmoniously coexist with human workers while contributing to the ecological transition of the sector.

HumanTech aims to achieve major advances in cutting-edge technologies that will enable a safe, rewarding, and digital work environment for a new generation of highly skilled construction workers and engineers.

These advances will include:

- **Robotic devices equipped with vision and intelligence** that allow them to navigate autonomously and safely in highly unstructured environments, collaborate with humans and dynamically update a semantic digital twin of the construction site in which they are working.
- **Smart, unobtrusive workers protection and support equipment.** From exoskeletons activated by body sensors for posture and strain to wearable cameras and XR glasses that provide real-time workers' location and guidance for them to perform their tasks efficiently and accurately.

- An entirely new breed of **Dynamic Semantic Digital Twins (DSDTs) of construction sites** that simulate in detail the current state of a construction site at the geometric and semantic level, based on an extended Building Information Modelling (BIM) formulation that contains all relevant structural and semantic dimensions (BIMxD). BIMxDs will act as a common reference for all human workers, engineers, and autonomous machines.

The **HumanTech consortium** is formed more than 20 organisations — leading research institutes and universities, innovative hi-tech SMEs, and large enterprises, construction groups and a construction SME representative — from 10 countries, bringing expertise in 11 different disciplines. The consortium is led by the German Research Centre for Artificial Intelligence's Augmented Vision department.

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1. Introduction

In this deliverable, the results of the HT micro-learning unit descriptors are outlined. These micro-learning units have been created based on the work proposed and carried out up to this point (December 2023) within the HT project and have been shared and validated with and by the project partners.

This work relates to WP6 “Human Factors - Training and Usability Assessment” and specifically to Task 6.1 (Micro-learning units' development and coordination). This task runs between month 10 and 35 with Deliverable 6.1 due in month 20. All partners have been consulted with extensively in the co-creation of the micro-learning units, both online and in person.

The objective of this task is to create an outline of:

- The micro learning units are expected to be delivered
- What Unit of Learning Outcome (ULOs) relates to each of these modules
- How these modules will be delivered
- To which discipline they will be delivered
- What content is expected to be included within these modules
- What resources are available and how this information will be utilised when creating these learning units.

The results presented in this report will go on to inform the further development of these learning units and support D6.2 (Training monitoring and evaluation report) due in month 35.

2. Methodology

2.1 Micro Learning Units

The learning units created within the HT project were to be created utilising the project goals, specifically relying on the pilot sites as guides for what must be included. The construction sector is among the least digitalised¹ therefore the training created within the HT projects has significant potential to have a positive impact on the construction sector. Digitalisation in the construction sector will focus on upskilling and reskilling the current and future workforce.

¹ European Construction Sector Observatory - Improving the human capital basis (2020), p. 7

The learning units created within the HT project will focus on not only the trainees but also the trainers. The learning units and training materials should assist and support trainers to deliver more flexible and innovative ways of upskilling. The materials created should be adaptable and be easily integrated into existing training to further enhance the training already being provided in higher education (HE), vocational education and training (VET) or in industry through continued professional development (CPD).

As per the HT grant agreement (GA) 10 to 16 Micro-Learning Units (MLU's) are targeted to be developed within the HT project within WP6. These will be presented as Open Educational Resources (OER) to be utilised throughout Europe. The development of these MLU's will be a collaborative process, utilising both industry and educational expertise within the HT project. Through this collaborative process, a focus will be emphasised on sustainability within the construction sector and Health and Safety.

The main thematic focus areas of this training will be:

- Technologies supporting workers safety and well-being in future digital construction
- Human Robot Collaboration in construction automation

2.2 Units of Learning Outcome

Based on the modules created (10 to 16), each will be associated with a unique unit of learning outcome (ULO) describing what the learner can expect to learn within each of the MLUs. These ULOs will broadly describe what each MLU contains and how this learning will be of use to the learners and how they can expect to apply this to their work.

2.3 Delivery Method

The training must be deliverable utilising a flexible delivery method, meaning the material must be usable in a variety of modalities such as in class, on-line, on-site, in-house and/or blended. This is due to the training being suitable for delivery to HEI, VET and to industry trainees. The HT project will make use of a pre-existing E-Learning platforms created by TUS for the Construction Blueprint² project. Construction Blueprint was a European project (2019-2023), belonging to the Erasmus+ Programme, for

² [Home - Construction Blueprint](#)

implementing a new strategic approach to sectoral cooperation on skills. We are a partnership formed by 24 partners from 12 countries, led by Fundación Laboral de la Construcción (Spain). New learning content for VET was devised in the areas of energy efficiency, circular economy and digitisation, with 45 new modules of micro learning units developed in total in addition to 75 MOOCs (Massive Online Open Content). Both HT partners TUS and EBC were partners in Construction Blueprint.

WP6 will closely collaborate with Task 8.2, Dissemination and Communication, to ensure the training modules are properly promoted and disseminated. A new page on the HumanTech website called Training will be created; on this page, all the training material, learning outcomes any other training materials created will be uploaded making it easily accessible for trainers, training centres and individuals to follow.

In parallel to this, WP8 will organise specific promotional activities, such as:

- Ad hoc social media campaigns, composed of specific posts and short video interviews and impact testimonials;
- Emailing campaigns: ad hoc stakeholders will be given information about the modules. These campaigns will be accompanied by specific PR material, such as short explanatory flyers and/or one-pager;
- Newsletters and press releases: at least two project newsletters will be released (Brevo and LinkedIn) and a press release created and disseminated;
- WP8 will promote the modules on the Tech4EUConstruction cluster and will start joint dissemination campaigns with the other members;
- The partners will take advantage of conferences, events, workshops etc. to promote the modules.

2.4 Learning Unit Content

The content for the learning units will be sourced mainly from the HT project outputs. This will be driven by the findings presented in the HT deliverables and work packages, papers created as outputs by HT partners and pilot site results.

2.5 Available Resource Collection

The HT project continues to focus on materials created within the project's timeframe. Specifically, deliverables and pilot sites will be elaborated as training content (as case studies where possible), as well as expertise and training already created or supplied by project partners (both industry and educational). And finally, the HT project will make use of existing e-learning platforms and freely available training materials which can be integrated into the learning units. This freely available training material will be derived from other European Funded projects such as Construction Blueprint and BIMzeED³ (and fully credited) and should be edited and updated following consultation with HT project partners.

2.6 Steps in Creating the MLU Descriptors

The method for creating the HT micro-learning unit descriptors follows four main steps. This process was collaborative and all partners in the HT project were consulted and informed of actions and decisions made within T6.1. These updates and consultations were provided on a monthly basis for members of WP6 and quarterly for all other partners unless and will continue to the end of the project with additions in communication as it becomes necessary.

The following is an outline of the process carried out by TUS in order to create the HT micro-learning unit descriptors as well as begin the creation of MLUs.

Step 1. Based on the HT project aims focus areas for where training material would be most valuable in order to upskill the workforce on digitalisation in construction. These target areas will relate to the HT main goals and objectives. These areas are 'Introduction to Digitalisation in the construction sector', 'BIM', 'Robotics and Imaging'. This was then shared with the HT partners for consultation and discussion in order to better understand where value can be added by the HT project and partners as well as further break down what must be included in these MLU's. Within this discussion the identification of target groups and EQF level and abilities and competencies were defined and discussed.

Step 2. Utilising the four categories highlighted in step one and creating groupings of initial ideas for what each MLU should include, the project partners were grouped in

³ [BIMzeED](#)

person in order to identify what is to be included. This took place in Barcelona in April 2023 and resulted in a wide range of information which then required organisation and further breakdown then leading to the initial list of MLU's being identified.

Step 3. The further breakdown of MLUs was then presented to the WP6 partners along with what each MLU is expected to cover. This was validated within WP6 and following this was presented to the entire consortium for further comments. The results of this can be seen in chapter 3, Results. Within this process, HT project partners were asked to identify where they felt they would be able to add most value to the MLUs by providing existing materials, sharing expertise or advise or providing materials or knowledge gained within the HT project.

Step 4. Following the previous steps, the MLU titles were defined, titled and corresponding ULO's were created for each MLU. In the following chapter the results of this process are described, including the MLUs expected to be delivered, the relating ULO's, the delivery method, the content expected for each module and what resources will be utilised in order to create these MLU's over the course of the next 15 months.

3. Results

Following consultation, validation and collaboration with project partners, 14 MLU's and the resulting learning outcomes were created. All 14 MLU'S will be created in a way that facilitates in class, on-line, on-site, in-house and blended learning. This is in order for the training to be deliverable to HE, VET and within industry.

Table 1: The MLU's along with their corresponding content and ULO's. It is important to note that project partners as well as project results are expected to facilitate the creation of these modules. Partners will be asked to share expertise, materials and later validate the training material before it is carried out. It is also expected that HT deliverables and pilot site results will be integrated into the training material when they become available.

Three training modules have now been created and are available to view on the Zenodo platform. These modules are in draft form and further edits will be made following reviews and test carried out with trainers. Please see the modules using the following links:

Module 1: <https://zenodo.org/records/10518691>

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Module 2: <https://zenodo.org/records/10518723>

Module 3: <https://zenodo.org/records/10518742>

Module	Title	ULO	Content
1	HumanTech and Digitalisation	Upon completion of this MLU trainers/trainees will be able to identify and understand the aims, opportunities and outcomes of both the HumanTech project and digitalisation in general. The learner will be able to define the benefits of human centred robotics, wearables and digital tools in the construction sector, specifically in improving workers safety and to support a greener industry.	An introduction to digitalisation The HumanTech Project HumanTech pilot sites and goals Reference architecture
2	Green Technology in Construction	Upon completion of this MLU trainers/trainees will be able to identify what opportunities are available when utilising digitalisation in order to support a green transition in the construction sector.	Introduction to sustainability (This will include an introduction to topics such as digitalisation for material impact reduction and the circular economy) How HumanTech processes can be applied for a greener industry
3	BIM Fundamentals	Upon completion of this MLU trainers/trainees will gain and understanding of BIM fundamentals and will therefore be able to apply BIM within their work while understanding the benefits in relation to efficiency, communication, sustainability, health and safety and more.	Introduction to BIM How BIM can be implemented for designers and onsite workers Existing BIM tools and their application (BIMxD will be given as an example) HumanTech pilot site examples
4	BIM management/ Common Data Environments (CDE)	Upon completion of this MLU trainers/trainees will gain an understanding of BIM management tools and their application relating to the construction sector.	An introduction to BIM management Common Data Environments (CDE) Cloud Coordination (BIM on Cloud) International Foundation Class (IFC)
5	bSDD	Upon completion of this MLU trainers/trainees will gain an understanding of buildingSMART Data Dictionaries and the learner should be able to apply this knowledge to their work.	Introduction to buildingSMART Data Dictionaries (bSDD) Application of bSDD Relation to HumanTech processes and methods

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6	Digital Twins	Upon completion of this MLU trainers/trainees will be able to identify the benefits of applying digital twins within the construction sector. The learner will be presented with on-site examples of digital twin application and therefore will understand how these can be applied within their own work.	An introduction to digital twins The Application of Digital Twins in the construction sector HumanTech pilot examples of Digital Twins on site
7	Scan to BIM and Imaging	Upon completion of this MLU trainers/trainees will be able to identify the methods and applications available for scan to BIM and imaging in construction. Learners will be presented with case study examples of Scan to BIM and imaging relating to the HumanTech project and therefore they will become familiar with the necessary processes and requirements for applying these tools.	An introduction to scan to BIM and its benefits within the construction sector Point clouds and imaging for BIM HumanTech pilot examples of scan to BIM on site
8	XR	Upon completion of this MLU trainers/trainees will gain an understanding of Extended Reality and its application within the construction sector, specifically for visualising construction projects for health and safety.	Introduction to Extended Reality (XR) XR's application and uses within the construction sector HumanTech pilot examples of XR on site
9	Robotics in Construction	Upon completion of this MLU trainers/trainees will gain an understanding of the benefits and application of robotics in construction. Learners will be presented with a pilot example of robotics on-site which will allow them to understand how robotics can be integrated to support the health and safety of workers.	Introduction to Robotics and their application within the construction sector HumanTech pilot examples of Robotics on site
10	UAV and UGV and construction	Upon completion of this MLU trainers/trainees will gain an understanding of the benefits and application of UAV's and UGV's in construction in order to reduce human risk and increase accuracy and efficiency.	Introduction to Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV) and Unmanned Ground Vehicles (UGV) and their application in the construction sector HumanTech pilot examples of UAV's and UGV's on site

11	360 Cameras and mounting on Robotics and Drones	Upon completion of this MLU trainers/trainees will gain an understanding of the benefits of 360 Cameras and mounting on Robotics and Drones. Trainees will be presented a case study to clearly illustrate the necessary steps to carry out this process.	Introduction to 360 cameras and their application within construction Application of mounting cameras Lidar and sensors on site HumanTech pilot examples of 360 Cameras and mounting on Robotics and Drones on site
12	Exoskeleton	Upon completion of this MLU trainers/trainees will gain an understanding of the human benefits to exoskeleton suits, in particular the reduction of repetitive strain injury and similar common on-site construction related injuries.	Introduction to exoskeletons and their application within construction HumanTech pilot examples of Exoskeleton on site

Table 1: MLU's

4. Summary of Next Steps

Following the completion of D6.1 HT micro-learning unit descriptors, Task 6.1 will continue. The goal of this task is the Micro-learning units' development and coordination. Continued consultation and communication will be carried out while these MLU's are being created in order to add value to the training materials provided by the HT project.

A training delivery plan along with a handbook for trainers will be designed with partners in 2024, in order to deliver the training units, to ensure quality and satisfaction of both trainers and learners in the content and to meet the training key performance indicators of the HT project.

